

Volumetric, viscometric and refractometric studies of glycine, alanine, valine and glycyglycine in aquo-sucrose solution at different temperatures

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Abstract : The densities, ρ , viscosities, η and refractive indices, n_D of (0.01, 0.05, 0.10, 0.15 and 0.20 *m*) glycine (Gly), DL-alanine (Ala), DL-valine (Val) and glycyglycine (Gly-Gly) in 0.10 *m* aquo-sucrose solution were measured at different temperatures. The apparent molar volume, ϕ_v , partial molar volume, ϕ_v^0 and volumes of transfer, $\phi_v^0(\text{tr})$ were calculated using density data. The viscosity data were analyzed using Jones-Dole equation to obtain viscosity coefficients. *A*- and *B*-, free energy of activation per mole of solvent, $\Delta\mu_1^{0*}$ and solute, $\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$. The refractive index data were used to compute molar refractivity, R_D of amino acids/peptide in aquo-sucrose solutions. The results were discussed in terms of interactions occurring in the ternary solution and the structure-making/-breaking ability of solute (amino acid/peptide) in aquo-sucrose solution.

Keywords : Density, viscosity, refractive index, amino acid/glycyglycine in aquo-sucrose solution, interactions.

Introduction

In living organisms, carbohydrates are the main source for doing mechanical work and chemical reaction. They are also assembled into polysaccharides for use as fuel storage and structural elements of co-factors (e.g. ATP, NADPH etc.), glycoproteins and polynucleotides¹. Carbohydrates act as receptors for biologically active compounds such as enzymes, hormones, viruses and antibodies²⁻⁴. Amino acids which are the basic components of proteins, interact with carbohydrates and play an important role in various biochemical processes, such as in immunology, pharmacology, biosynthesis and medicine⁵. Literature survey reveals that the thermodynamic studies on carbohydrate-protein interactions are quite rare⁶⁻⁸.

The present study is an extension of our earlier work⁹ on amino acid-carbohydrate interaction in aqueous medium. In the present investigation we have taken densities, viscosities and refractive indices of three amino acids, glycine, alanine and valine and one peptide, glycyglycine in aquo-sucrose solution as a function of amino acid/peptide concentration at different temperatures. These data are used to evaluate various useful thermodynamic parameters which provide an insight into the interactions occurring in amino acid/peptide-carbohydrate-

water solutions and the nature of solute (amino acids/peptide) on such interactions.

Results and discussion

The densities, ρ , viscosities, η and refractive indices, n_D of (0.01, 0.05, 0.10, 0.15 and 0.20 *m*) Gly, Ala, Val and Gly-Gly in 0.1 *m* aquo-sucrose solution were determined at 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K, and are given in Table 1. The density data were used to compute apparent molar volume, ϕ_v using the equation,

$$\phi_v = \frac{M}{\rho} - \frac{1000(\rho - \rho_0)}{m\rho\rho_0} \quad (1)$$

where *m* is the molality of solute (amino acid/peptide) having molecular weight, *M*. The ϕ_v values are given in Table 2. It is evident from Table 2 that ϕ_v is a linear function of molality of amino acid/peptide.

The limiting apparent molar volume, ϕ_v^0 (same as partial molar volume at infinite dilution or standard partial molar volume) was obtained by least-squares fitting of ϕ_v values to the equation,

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^0 + S_v^* m^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

where S_v^* is the experimental slope, which is considered to be the volumetric pairwise interaction coefficient^{10,11}.

Table-1 (contd.)

Table 1. Values of density, ρ , viscosity, η and refractive index, n_D of glycine, alanine, valine and glycylglycine in aquo-sucrose solution at different temperatures										
m (mol kg ⁻¹)	T (K)									
	298.15	303.15	308.15	313.15						
	Gly + aquo-sucrose				0.20	1.3418	1.3408	1.3400	1.3394	
	ρ (kg m ⁻³)					Val + aquo-sucrose				
0.00	1010.1	1008.4	1006.8	1005.1	0.00	1010.1	1008.4	1006.8	1005.1	
0.01	1010.5	1008.7	1007.0	1005.2	0.01	1010.5	1008.7	1007.0	1005.2	
0.05	1012.0	1009.8	1007.7	1005.5	0.05	1012.0	1009.8	1007.8	1005.6	
0.10	1013.6	1010.9	1008.4	1005.8	0.10	1013.6	1011.0	1008.7	1006.0	
0.15	1014.8	1011.7	1008.9	1006.0	0.15	1015.0	1012.0	1009.5	1006.3	
0.20	1015.7	1012.4	1009.2	1006.2	0.20	1016.1	1013.0	1010.1	1006.6	
	$10^3 \times \eta$ (Ns m ⁻²)					$10^3 \times \eta$ (Ns m ⁻²)				
0.00	0.9775	0.8732	0.7860	0.7129	0.00	0.9775	0.8747	0.7897	0.7178	
0.01	0.9823	0.8766	0.7883	0.7144	0.01	0.9920	0.8856	0.7971	0.7229	
0.05	0.9897	0.8821	0.7926	0.7175	0.05	1.0158	0.9046	0.8118	0.7339	
0.10	0.9968	0.8878	0.7969	0.7211	0.10	1.0405	0.9240	0.8279	0.7476	
0.15	1.0028	0.8929	0.8015	0.7248	0.15	1.0623	0.9428	0.8442	0.7617	
0.20	1.0095	0.8984	0.8064	0.7284	0.20	1.0838	0.9615	0.8605	0.7763	
	n_D					n_D				
0.00	1.3345	1.3341	1.3338	1.3332	0.00	1.3348	1.3341	1.3338	1.3332	
0.01	1.3348	1.3344	1.3341	1.3336	0.01	1.3352	1.3349	1.3345	1.3343	
0.05	1.3362	1.3357	1.3354	1.3349	0.05	1.3370	1.3367	1.3364	1.3363	
0.10	1.3378	1.3372	1.3368	1.3362	0.10	1.3389	1.3386	1.3384	1.3379	
0.15	1.3394	1.3387	1.3381	1.3374	0.15	1.3407	1.3405	1.3401	1.3396	
0.20	1.3407	1.3400	1.3393	1.3386	0.20	1.3427	1.3424	1.3417	1.3411	
	Ala + aquo-sucrose					Gly-Gly + aquo-sucrose				
	ρ (kg m ⁻³)					ρ (kg m ⁻³)				
0.00	1010.1	1008.4	1006.8	1005.1	0.00	1010.1	1008.4	1006.8	1005.1	
0.01	1010.5	1008.7	1007.0	1005.2	0.01	1010.8	1009.0	1007.3	1005.5	
0.05	1012.0	1009.8	1007.7	1005.5	0.05	1013.3	1011.1	1009.1	1006.9	
0.10	1013.7	1011.0	1008.5	1005.8	0.10	1015.8	1013.2	1010.8	1008.2	
0.15	1015.3	1012.0	1009.1	1006.0	0.15	1017.9	1014.8	1012.0	1009.0	
0.20	1016.7	1013.1	1009.6	1006.1	0.20	1019.6	1015.9	1012.7	1009.5	
	$10^3 \times \eta$ (Ns m ⁻²)					$10 \times \eta$ (Ns m ⁻²)				
0.00	0.9775	0.8732	0.7860	0.7129	0.00	0.9767	0.8732	0.7860	0.7129	
0.01	0.9835	0.8775	0.7891	0.7150	0.01	0.9857	0.8796	0.7907	0.7162	
0.05	0.9967	0.8882	0.7981	0.7224	0.05	1.0009	0.8915	0.7998	0.7227	
0.10	1.0109	0.9004	0.8084	0.7311	0.10	1.0153	0.9035	0.8101	0.7309	
0.15	1.0240	0.9111	0.8184	0.7395	0.15	1.0294	0.9149	0.8195	0.7385	
0.20	1.0362	0.9215	0.8269	0.7472	0.20	1.0414	0.9262	0.8290	0.7475	
	n_D					n_D				
0.00	1.3345	1.3341	1.3338	1.3332	0.00	1.3345	1.3341	1.3338	1.3332	
0.01	1.3349	1.3345	1.3341	1.3338	0.01	1.3350	1.3347	1.3342	1.3338	
0.05	1.3367	1.3362	1.3357	1.3352	0.05	1.3371	1.3366	1.3361	1.3355	
0.10	1.3386	1.3380	1.3374	1.3369	0.10	1.3393	1.3386	1.3380	1.3373	
0.15	1.3403	1.3395	1.3387	1.3382	0.15	1.3411	1.3403	1.3396	1.3388	
					0.20	1.3426	1.3417	1.3410	1.3402	

Errors in measured densities, viscosities and refractive indices are 0.01%, 0.3% and 0.02%, respectively.

Table 2. Values of ϕ_v of glycine, alanine, valine and glycyglycine in aquo-sucrose solution at different temperatures

<i>m</i> (mol kg ⁻¹)	<i>T</i> (K)			
	298.15	303.15	308.15	313.15
	$10^5 \times \phi_v$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)			
	Gly + aquo-sucrose			
0.01	3.5101	4.4929	5.4821	6.4784
0.05	3.7006	4.6844	5.6755	6.6744
0.10	3.9878	4.9736	5.8685	6.7713
0.15	4.3408	5.2637	6.0625	6.8688
0.20	4.6618	5.4560	6.2575	6.9169
	Ala + aquo-sucrose			
0.01	4.8976	5.8828	6.8744	7.8731
0.05	5.0860	6.0728	7.0667	8.0687
0.10	5.2728	6.2618	7.1596	8.1652
0.15	5.4272	6.3856	7.3194	8.2625
0.20	5.5493	6.4935	7.4470	8.3605
	Val + aquo-sucrose			
0.01	7.6744	8.6646	9.6609	10.665
0.05	7.8587	8.8516	9.6532	10.660
0.10	8.1393	9.0372	9.7431	10.755
0.15	8.3557	9.2243	9.8337	10.851
0.20	8.6064	9.3131	9.9754	10.897
	Gly-Gly + aquo-sucrose			
0.01	6.2149	7.1972	8.1860	9.1818
0.05	6.8838	7.7707	8.6442	9.5643
0.10	7.4513	8.3419	9.1403	10.045
0.15	7.9222	8.8499	9.6529	10.530
0.20	8.3459	9.3447	10.153	10.919

Fig. 1. Plots of S_v^* vs T for glycine, alanine, valine and glycyglycine in aquo-sucrose solution at different temperatures.

Standard partial molar volumes, ϕ_v^0 and S_v^* values are summarized in Table 3 and S_v^* is also graphically presented in Fig. 1. At infinite dilution, solute-solute interactions do not exist, therefore, ϕ_v^0 provides information regarding solute-solvent interactions¹², whereas, information concerning solute-solute interactions is given by S_v^* . Table 3 reflects that values of ϕ_v^0 are large positive and greater than the values of S_v^* , thereby, suggesting the presence of strong solute-solvent (amino acid-water/sucrose) interactions and weak solute-solute (amino acid-amino acid) interactions. The increase in ϕ_v^0 with temperature may be attributed to the reduced electrostriction of water due to zwitterionic groups of amino acids/peptide.

Generally, the interactions which are expected to occur in amino acids/peptide + aquo-sucrose solution can be classified as¹³⁻¹⁸.

(a) The zwitterionic group (NH_3^+ , COO^-) of amino acids/peptide are hydrated in electrostatic manner while the hydration of intervening backbone depends on its hydrophobic, hydrophilic or amphiphilic character.

(b) NH_3^+ group has greater electrostriction effect than COO^- group by a factor of ≈ 10 .

(c) The overlap of hydration cospheres of terminal zwitterionic groups (NH_3^+ and COO^-) and adjacent groups results in volume change.

The ϕ_v^0 value is found to increase with decrease in the electrostriction at the terminals whereas it decreases with disruption of side group hydration by that of the charged end. The observed ϕ_v^0 values (Table 3) are found to increase as the size of alkyl group in the amino acid increases from glycine to valine. The increase in ϕ_v^0 from glycine to valine is due to the increase in hydrophobicity (non-polar character) of side chain as H-atom in Gly is replaced by a hydrophobic group, $-\text{CH}_3$ in Ala and by a more hydrophobic group, $-\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$ in Val. As a consequence of (b), the more freer *N*-terminal in Gly would cause the largest volume contraction, followed by Ala and then by Val due to increased shielding of *N*-terminal in the latter two amino acids for electrostriction. As the Gly-Gly molecule is more hydrophobic than Gly molecule, there would be less contraction in volume due to electrostriction of water by its end groups (NH_3^+ , COO^-) than in case of Gly, resulting in larger ϕ_v^0 values

Table 3. Values of ϕ_v^0 , $\phi_{v(tr)}^0$ and S_v^* of glycine, alanine, valine and glycyglycine in aquo-sucrose solution at different temperatures

T (K)	$10^5 \times \phi_v^0$ ($m^3 mol^{-1}$)	$10^5 \times \phi_{v(aq)}^0$ ($m^3 mol^{-1}$)	$10^5 \times \phi_{v(tr)}^0$ ($m^3 mol^{-1}$)	$10^5 \times S_v^*$ ($m^3 mol^{-2} kg$)
Gly + aquo-sucrose				
298.15	3.0652 ± 0.021	4.3200^a	-1.2548	3.3065 ± 0.028
303.15	4.1334 ± 0.023	-	-	2.8513 ± 0.047
308.15	5.2179 ± 0.011	4.3800^b	-0.2466	2.2089 ± 0.051
313.15	6.3690 ± 0.040	4.4000^c	1.9690	1.2647 ± 0.032
Ala + aquo-sucrose				
298.15	4.6869 ± 0.021	6.0500^c	-1.3631	1.8979 ± 0.061
303.15	5.6940 ± 0.019	-	-	1.7813 ± 0.020
308.15	6.7003 ± 0.031	6.1010^c	0.5993	1.6044 ± 0.034
313.15	7.7442 ± 0.022	6.1200^c	1.6242	1.3625 ± 0.049
Val + aquo-sucrose				
298.15	7.3364 ± 0.010	9.0980^c	-1.7616	2.6807 ± 0.028
303.15	8.4494 ± 0.025	-	-	1.9288 ± 0.024
308.15	9.5139 ± 0.026	9.1550^c	0.3589	0.8795 ± 0.025
313.15	10.5510 ± 0.017	9.1670^d	1.3840	0.7284 ± 0.012
Gly-Gly + aquo-sucrose				
298.15	5.5566 ± 0.023	7.6280^c	-2.0714	6.1280 ± 0.019
303.15	6.4849 ± 0.032	-	-	6.1584 ± 0.022
308.15	7.4981 ± 0.020	7.7100^c	-0.2219	5.6201 ± 0.014
313.15	8.5572 ± 0.035	-	-	5.0565 ± 0.021

^aRef. 22, ^bRef. 21, ^cRef. 19, ^dRef. 23, ^eRef. 24.

for Gly-Gly than for Gly (Table 3). Similar increasing trend in ϕ_v^0 values with side chain have also been reported by Banipal and Kapoor¹⁹ in aqueous solution of amino acids.

The decrease in the values of S_v^* (Table 3) with increase in temperature for all the amino acids/peptide, also indicates that all the amino acids/peptide in the present study behave as structure-breakers²⁰ in presence of sucrose in aqueous solutions.

The partial molar volumes of transfer, $\phi_{v(tr)}^0$ of amino acid/peptide from water to aquo-sucrose solution were determined from ϕ_v^0 data using the relation,

$$\phi_{v(tr)}^0 = \phi_v^0(\text{aq. sucrose}) - \phi_v^0(\text{aq.}) \quad (3)$$

The values of $\phi_{v(tr)}^0$ are summarized in Table 3 and graphically presented in Fig. 2. The $\phi_v^0(\text{aq.})$ for amino acids/peptide were taken from the literature^{19,21-24}. It is observed (Table 3) that $\phi_v^0(\text{aq.})$ values for all the three amino acids are found to be negative at lower temperature but become positive as the temperature increases. While, large

Fig. 2. Plots of $\phi_{v(tr)}^0$ vs T for glycine, alanine, valine and glycyglycine in aquo-sucrose solution at different temperatures.

negative $\phi_{v(tr)}^0$ values are obtained for the peptide. The results can be explained in the light of cosphere overlap model proposed by Friedman and Krishnan²⁵, which states that the overlap of hydration cospheres is destructive.

This model was further extended by Mishra *et al.*¹⁶. They observed that the overlapping of cospheres of two ionic species lead to a positive $\phi_{v(tr)}^0$ value due to decreased electrostriction because the overall water structure is enhanced, whereas, the reduction in volume is observed due to the overlapping of ion-hydrophobic groups and hydrophobic-hydrophobic groups, leading to negative $\phi_{v(tr)}^0$ values. Therefore, it is interpreted that ion-hydrophobic and hydrophobic-hydrophobic interactions dominate over ion-hydrophilic interaction at low temperature, while the reverse is the case at higher temperature. On the other hand, dominance of ion-hydrophobic and hydrophobic-hydrophobic interactions over ion-hydrophilic interactions is found in case of Gly-Gly with large negative $\phi_{v(tr)}^0$ values.

The ϕ_{v}^0 of amino acid/peptide can also be viewed as^{27,28}

$$\phi_{v(tr)}^0 = V_{vw} + V_{void} + V_{shrinkage} \quad (4)$$

where V_{vw} is the van der Waals volume^{29,30}, V_{void} is the void or empty volume arising because of the thermal motion and packing effect³¹ and $V_{shrinkage}$ is shrinkage in volume due to the interaction of solute with the solvent. $V_{vw} + V_{void}$ is transfer intrinsic volume of solute from water to aquo-sucrose solvent, and it is assumed that V_{vw} and V_{void} remain of the same magnitude in water and in mixed solvent³², then the positive $\phi_{v(tr)}^0$ for Gly, Ala and Val can be attributed to the decrease in the volume of shrinkage due the presence of these solute molecules in aqueous solutions, while, negative $\phi_{v(tr)}^0$ for Gly-Gly is due to increase in volume of shrinkage.

The viscosity data was analysed with the help of Jones-Dole equation³³,

$$\eta_r = \frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = 1 + Am^{1/2} + Bm \quad (5)$$

where η_r is the relative viscosity, m is the molal concentration of solute (amino acid/peptide). A is the Falkenhagen coefficient, a measure of solute-solute interactions³⁴ and B , the Jones-Dole coefficient is an empirical constant and is indicative of solute-solvent interactions. The viscosity coefficients, A and B , were calculated from the intercepts and slopes of the plots of $(\eta_r - 1)/m^{1/2}$ vs $m^{1/2}$. The plots of $(\eta_r - 1)/m^{1/2}$ vs $m^{1/2}$ for amino acids and peptide at 298.15 K are given in Fig. 3, as the plots at remaining

Fig. 3. Plots of $(\eta_r - 1)/m^{1/2}$ vs $m^{1/2}$ for glycine, alanine, valine and glycyglycine in aquo-sucrose solution at 298.15 K.

temperatures show similar trends. The values of A - and B -coefficients are summarized in Table 4. Table 4 shows that B -coefficient values are positive and larger than those of A -coefficients, suggesting the presence of strong solute-solvent interactions as compared to solute-solute interactions.

Eyring and co-workers³⁵ proposed the following relation for the calculation of the free energy of activation of viscous flow per mole of solvent, $\Delta\mu_1^{0*}$,

$$\eta_0 = \frac{hN_A}{V_1^0} \exp\left(\frac{\Delta\mu_1^{0*}}{RT}\right) \quad (6)$$

where h is the Planck's constant, N_A is the Avogadro's number, R is the universal gas constant, T is the temperature and V_1^0 is the partial molar volume of solvent.

Rearrangement of above equation yields,

$$\Delta\mu_1^{0*} = RT \ln\left(\frac{\eta_0 V_1^0}{hN_A}\right) \quad (7)$$

Based on Eyring transition state theory³⁵, Feakins *et al.*¹⁶ obtained the following equation for the free energy of activation of viscous flow per mole of solute, $\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$,

$$B = \frac{(\bar{V}_1^0) - (\bar{V}_2^0)}{1000} + \frac{\bar{V}_1^0 (\Delta\mu_2^{0*} - \Delta\mu_1^{0*})}{1000 RT} \quad (8)$$

where \bar{V}_2^0 ($=\phi_v^0$) is the partial molar volume of the solute. Eq. (8) can be rearranged as follows,

$$\Delta\mu_2^{0*} = \Delta\mu_1^{0*} + \left(\frac{RT}{\bar{V}_1^0}\right) \left[1000B - (\bar{V}_1^0 - \bar{V}_2^0)\right] \quad (9)$$

The values of $\Delta\mu_1^{0*}$ and $\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$ are also included in Table 4.

Table 4 shows that the values of $\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$ are greater than $\Delta\mu_1^{0*}$, suggesting that the probability of formation of transition state is less favourable in the presence of aquo-sucrose solution due to breaking and distortion of the intermolecular bonds. The $\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$ increases in the order : Gly < Gly-Gly < Ala < Val, implying that the solvation of amino acids/peptide having longer alkyl chain or greater hydrophobicity become increasing unfavourable and require more energy in transferring from ground to transition state. Therefore, for the formation of transition state, more solute-solvent bonds are broken. Similar results were also reported by Pal *et al.*²⁰ for Gly, Ala and Val in aquo-urea solutions and also by Ali *et al.*³⁷ for Gly, Ala, Val and Ser in aquo-glucose solutions.

The refractive index data is utilized in the computa-

tion of molar refractivity, R_D , using Lorentz-Lorenz equation,

$$R_D = \left(\frac{n_D^2 - 1}{n_D^2 + 1}\right) \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^3 x_i M_i}{\rho}\right) \quad (10)$$

where x_i is the mole fraction and M_i , the molecular weight of the i -th component of the mixture. The values of R_D are given in Table 5. The variation of R_D with molality of amino acids/peptide is plotted in Fig. 4 at a single temperature ($T = 303.15$ K) because there is not much variation in the R_D values with temperature. As R_D is directly proportional to molecular polarizability, Fig. 4 depicts that the overall polarizability of the three amino acids, Gly, Ala and Val and peptide, Gly-Gly increases with increasing amount of amino acid/peptide in the mixture. These results are in good agreement with those reported by Ali *et al.*^{9,37} for α -amino acids in aquo-D-glucose solution and in aqueous tetrapropylammonium bromide solutions.

Table 4. Values of Falkenhagen coefficients, A , Jones-Dole coefficients, B , free energies of activation per mole of solvent, $\Delta\mu_1^{0*}$ and solute, $\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$ of glycine, alanine, valine and glycyglycine in aquo-sucrose solution at different temperatures

T (K)	$10^2 \times A$ ($\text{dm}^{3/2} \text{mol}^{-1/2}$)	$10^2 \times B$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	$\Delta\mu_1^{0*}$ (kJ mol^{-1})	$\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$ (kJ mol^{-1})
Gly + aquo-sucrose				
298.15	4.1 ± 0.01	6.9 ± 0.04	9.44	20.39
303.15	3.1 ± 0.02	7.3 ± 0.05	9.32	22.42
308.15	2.0 ± 0.02	8.0 ± 0.06	9.20	25.02
313.15	1.1 ± 0.01	8.1 ± 0.03	9.10	26.94
Ala + aquo-sucrose				
298.15	4.0 ± 0.02	21.2 ± 0.09	9.44	41.91
303.15	2.9 ± 0.02	21.5 ± 0.06	9.32	44.05
308.15	1.8 ± 0.02	22.4 ± 0.06	9.20	46.99
313.15	0.7 ± 0.02	22.8 ± 0.05	9.10	49.53
Val + aquo-sucrose				
298.15	11.8 ± 0.03	27.5 ± 0.09	9.44	53.96
303.15	9.3 ± 0.03	28.1 ± 0.07	9.32	56.76
308.15	5.9 ± 0.04	30.8 ± 0.06	9.22	62.58
313.15	3.4 ± 0.06	32.1 ± 0.05	9.12	66.63
Gly-Gly + aquo-sucrose				
298.15	7.5 ± 0.04	16.2 ± 0.05	9.44	36.35
303.15	5.5 ± 0.09	17.7 ± 0.03	9.32	39.93
308.15	4.0 ± 0.10	18.0 ± 0.06	9.20	42.10
313.15	2.4 ± 0.04	18.1 ± 0.07	9.10	44.08

Table 5. Values of molar refractive index, R_D , of glycine, alanine, valine and glycyglycine in aquo-sucrose solution at different temperatures

m (mol kg ⁻¹)	T (K)			
	298.15	303.15	308.15	313.15
$10^6 \times R_D$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)				
Gly + aquo-sucrose				
0.00	3.7996	3.8019	3.8048	3.8051
0.01	3.8013	3.8040	3.8073	3.8089
0.05	3.8105	3.8136	3.8185	3.8217
0.10	3.8214	3.8254	3.8308	3.8345
0.15	3.8338	3.8383	3.8428	3.8467
0.20	3.8442	3.8495	3.8545	3.8588
Ala + aquo-sucrose				
0.00	3.7996	3.8019	3.8048	3.8051
0.01	3.8024	3.8050	3.8073	3.8110
0.05	3.8157	3.8189	3.8217	3.8249
0.10	3.8295	3.8335	3.8369	3.8420
0.15	3.8417	3.8454	3.8486	3.8553
0.20	3.8521	3.8556	3.8607	3.8680
Val + aquo-sucrose				
0.00	3.8027	3.8019	3.8048	3.8051
0.01	3.8055	3.8092	3.8115	3.8163
0.05	3.8191	3.8243	3.8288	3.8362
0.10	3.8334	3.8402	3.8469	3.8521
0.15	3.8475	3.8568	3.8623	3.8694
0.20	3.8606	3.8734	3.8773	3.8846
Gly-Gly + aquo-sucrose				
0.00	3.7996	3.8019	3.8048	3.8051
0.01	3.8023	3.8060	3.8073	3.8100
0.05	3.8155	3.8185	3.8211	3.8231
0.10	3.8295	3.8322	3.8351	3.8378
0.15	3.8410	3.8446	3.8480	3.8512
0.20	3.8509	3.8557	3.8608	3.8648

Experimental

The amino acids glycine (E. Merck, mass fraction 0.99), DL-alanine and DL-valine (both from Loba Chemie, mass fractions 0.99 and 0.996, respectively), and peptide, glycyglycine (Acros, mass fraction 0.99) were used after recrystallization from aquo-ethanol solution. They were stored over P₂O₅ in a dessicator before use. Analytical reagent grade sucrose (E. Merck, mass fraction > 0.99) was used after recrystallization in order to attain maximum purity and was dried in vacuum. Doubly distilled and deionized water was used for the preparation of solutions. The ternary solutions of glycine, DL-alanine,

Fig. 4. Plots of R_D vs m for glycine, alanine, valine and glycyglycine in aquo-sucrose solution at 303.15 K.

DL-valine and glycyglycine (0.01–0.20) m in 0.1 m aquo-sucrose solution were prepared, all on the molality basis. The weighings were done on Precisa XB-220A (Swiss-make electronic balance) having a precision of $\pm 1 \times 10^{-4}$ g. The solutions were kept in special air tight bottles to avoid contamination and evaporation.

Density measurements were performed using pycnometer having graduated capillary of narrow bore. It is provided with a well-fitted glass cap in order to avoid changes in composition because of evaporation. The accuracy in density measurements was found to be ± 0.0001 g cm⁻³. The viscosity measurements were done by using a thoroughly cleaned and perfectly dried Ubbelohde type suspended level viscometer. The viscosity of ternary solution was calculated by using following equation,

$$\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = \frac{\rho t}{\rho_0 t_0}$$

where η and η_0 are the viscosities and ρ and ρ_0 are the densities of solution and solvent, respectively, t is the flow time of solution and t_0 for the solvent. The refractive index of amino acids/peptide in aquo-sucrose solution was also determined using Abbe refractometer after calibrating it with doubly distilled water and toluene at known temperature. The accuracy in refractive index measurements was up to ± 0.0002 .

Conclusion :

The values of ϕ_v^0 for Gly, Ala, Val and Gly-Gly are large positive and greater than S_v^* values, thereby, suggesting that solute-solvent interactions are stronger than solute-solute interactions in the present study. Further,

the increase in ϕ_v^0 from Gly to Val is attributed to the increased hydrophobicity of the side chain, a H-atom in Gly, is replaced by a hydrophobic group, $-\text{CH}_3$ in Ala, and even by a more hydrophobic group, $-\text{CH}-\text{CH}_3-\text{CH}_3$ in Val. Thus, causing least shielding of the end groups (NH_3^+ , COO^-) in Gly, followed by Ala, and maximum shielding in Val for electrostriction of the water molecules, resulting in the contraction in volume which follow the sequence : Gly > Ala > Val; hence, the increase in ϕ_v^0 from Gly to Val. Also, Gly-Gly molecule being more hydrophobic than Gly, exhibits larger ϕ_v^0 values. The partial molar volumes of transfer, $\phi_{v(\text{tr})}^0$ of all the three amino acids are negative at low temperature, become positive as the temperature increases. This suggests the dominance of ion-hydrophobic and hydrophobic-hydrophobic interactions over ion-hydrophilic interactions at lower temperature, whereas, an opposite trend is observed at higher temperature. In case of Gly-Gly, dominance of first two types of interactions over the third type is observed. Moreover, the values of $\Delta\mu_2^{0*}$ are larger than those of $\Delta\mu_1^{0*}$. This suggests that the formation of transition state is less favourable in presence of sucrose due to distortion of the intermolecular bonds. There is almost linear increase in the molar refractivity, R_D as the amount of amino acids/Gly-Gly increases, indicating overall increase in polarizability of these solutes in the solution.

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